

EFFECT OF INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF LINSEED UNDER SOUTH GUJARAT CONDITION

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(MS Received: 07.05.2023; MS Revised:09.06.2023; MS Accepted:10.06.2023)

MS 3036

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRONOMY)

Abstract

A field experiment was conducted on heavy black soil at the Department of Agronomy farm, N. M. College of Agriculture, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari (Gujarat) during rabi season -2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-21. The study consisted ten weed management practices viz. Weedy check (T_1), Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing (T_2), Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence (T_3), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence (T_4), Pre mix Pendimethalin + Imazethapyr @ 800g/ha as Pre emergence (T_5), Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence (T_6), Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence) (T_7), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence) (T_8), Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 days after sowing (T_9), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 days after sowing (T_{10}) were tested in randomized block design with three replications. Significantly higher seed yield and stover yield were recorded with Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing, but which was at par with Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS. The higher seed yield of 787, 1083, 870 and 913 kg/ha and higher stover yield of 2191, 2309, 2312 and 2271 kg/ha were recorded with the treatment T_2 (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) during the year 2018-19, 2019-20, 2020-21 and in pooled results, respectively. The highest weed control efficiency (70.36%) and lowest weed index (61.53%) was recorded with the treatment T_2 (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) followed by the treatment T_9 (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS).

Key words: Linseed, weed density, weeds dry weight, seed yield, stover yield, and economics.

Introduction

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) belongs to Linaceae family and is commonly known by different names viz. alsii, teesi, chikna or Linseed in India. It is a great source of nutrients and contains 33 to 47% of oil. Linseed oil is used in cooking as well as for industrial uses. Out of total oil produced, about 20% is used at farmer's level and the rest 80% oil goes to industries in various purposes such as borated oil, boiled oil, urethane oil, aluminates oil, epoxidized oil, isomerizes oil etc. The oil is rich in linolenic acid (>66%) and it is a perfect drying oil. Linseed contains high levels of dietary fiber as well as lignin, an abundance of micronutrient and omega-3 fatty acids. It tastes good and contains 36% protein, 85% of which is digestible. It is also used as organic manure and contains about 5% N, 1.4% P₂O₅ and 1.8% K₂O (J. B. et al., 2019). Linseed's essential fatty acids have anti-inflammatory properties, offering health benefits to a number of chronic diseases such as Heart disease, Diabetes and Arthritis (Sarkar and Sarkar, 2017)

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is an important rabi oilseed crop next to rapeseed and mustard in India (Badiyala et al., 2015). India is an important linseed growing country in the world and it contributes 7% to the world linseed pool. In India, linseed is cultivated in about 0.26 M ha with a contribution of 0.13 million tone to the annual oilseed production. The crop is being grown under input starve condition by the resource poor farmers. The productivity of linseed at national level is 523 kg ha⁻¹ (Anonymous 2017) while at experimental level it is 1800-2000 kg ha⁻¹. This gap in yield is due to poor management of inputs. Owing to poor initial growth, foliage and never forms a canopy; therefore it remains a poor weed competitor throughout its life. Because of slow initial growth and small sized leaves, the crop is highly infested by weeds causing 30-40% yield losses (Mahere et al. 2000). Yield losses to the tune of 49.7% in linseed due to severe infestation of field dodder have been reported. Flax does not compete well with weeds and therefore needs extensive management for effective weed control. Flax does not rapidly cover the soil surface allowing weeds to recruit later in the growing season and out-compete it for nutrients and space. Heavy infestations may even cause complete crop failures. In this context, several scientific

researches show that reduction or elimination of weed interference can increase linseed seed and oil yield. Conventionally, weeds are controlled by hand weeding and inter-culturing between the rows, but it involves more cost, which reduces profit gain. Therefore, the use of herbicides may be a suitable alternative for managing the weeds for higher returns (Singh et al. 2019). Some herbicides are extensively used as preemergence herbicide and some herbicides are used as postemergence for weed management in linseed field, but the efficacy of herbicides fluctuates according to the soil type, moisture regime, and types of weed flora. Therefore, for effective control of weeds in linseed, selected herbicide is needed with the integration of interculturing and hand weeding (Angiras et al., 1991)

Materials And Methods

A field experiment was conducted during rabi-2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-21 at Instructional farm, Department of N. M College of Agriculture, N. A. U., Navsari, Gujarat. The soil of the experimental site clayey in texture and PH was high (7.8). The soil was low in available nitrogen (197 kg/ha), medium in available phosphorus (52 kg/ha) and high in available potassium (481 kg/ha). The study consisted ten weed management practices viz. Weedy check (T_1), Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing (T_2), Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence (T_3), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence (T_4), Pre mix Pendimethalin + Imazethapyr @ 800g/ha as Pre emergence (T_5), Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence (T_6), Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence) (T_7), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds(Post emergence) (T_8), Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 days after sowing (T_9), Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 days after sowing (T_{10}). These treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Main field was prepared by two dry ploughing at an interval of 10 to 15 days followed by passing the harrow and leveler. The seeds of Local, 20 kg/ha was sown at the spacing of 30 cm line sowing. The recommended full dose 60:30:00 NPK kg/ha was applied as a basal dose.. The observation on Plant height (cm), Number of

branches per plant, Number of capsules per plant, Number of seeds per capsule, Seed weight per plant(g), Test weight, (g) Dry matter production per plant., Seed yield (kg/ha) Stover yield (kg/ha), Oil content (%), Protein content (%) were recorded at harvest and Weed count of grasses (No./m²), Weed count of BLW (No./m²), Weed

count of sedges (No./m²) were recorded at 40 DAS and at harvest. Since the data on weed density and weed dry weight showed high variation, the data were subjected to square root transformation and the statistical analysis was done. Weed index and weed control efficiency were calculated as per the standard formulae.

$$\text{Weed control efficiency} = \frac{\text{Dry matter production of weed in unweeded plot} - \text{Dry weight production of weeds in treated plot}}{\text{Dry matter production of weed in unweeded plot}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Weed control index} = \frac{\text{Yield from weed free plot} - \text{Yield from treatment plot}}{\text{Yield from weed free plot}} \times 100$$

Results And Discussion

The results obtained from the present investigation as well as relevant discussion have been summarized under following heads.

Table 1 : The different weed species were observed in the experiment plot

Sr. No	Botanical name	English name	Local name
A. Monocot weeds			
1	<i>Echinochloa crusgalli</i>	Barnyard grass	Bantiyo
2	<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Barnyard grass	Samo
3	<i>Dinebrare troflexa</i>	Viper grass	Khariyu
4	<i>Acrachne racemosa</i>	Goose grass	Chokhaliyu
B. Dicot weeds			
1	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i>	Giant pigweed	Patharchatta/ satodo
2	<i>Portulaca oleraceae</i>	Common purselane	Luni
3	<i>Euphorbia geniculata</i>	Spurge	Badi dudheli
4	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Garden spurge	Chhoti dudheli
5	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	Spiny amaranth	Kantalo dhimdo
6	<i>Abutilon indicum</i>	Indian Mallow	Kanski
7	<i>Physalis minima</i>	Ground cherry	Popti
8	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i>	Sessile joyweed	Khaki weed
9	<i>Digera arvensis Forsk</i>	False amaranth	kanajro
10	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Tridax daisy/ Mexican Daisy	Akdandi/ Bhangaro
C. Sedge			
1	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Nut sedge	Chidho

Weed density (No./m²)

The results of the experiment (Table 1) indicated that the different weed management treatments had significant effect on weed density at harvest in linseed crop during all the years as well as in pooled results.

Significantly the lowest weed count at harvest was recorded in the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) during 2018-19 (14.67 No./m²), 2019-20 (15.00 No./m²) and 2020-21 (40.33 No./m²) and in pooled results (23.33 No./m²) and followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS) during all the three years and in pooled results. While, significantly the highest weed count at harvest was observed in unweeded treatment (T₁) during 2018-19 (147.67 No./m²), 2019-20 (98.67 No./m²) and 2020-21 (121.33 No./m²) and in pooled results (122.56 No./m²). Husain et al. (2015) also observed lower weed count in hand weeding twice treatment compared to chemical weed control and weedy check in linseed.

Weed dry weight (g/m²)

An appraisal of data in Table 1 indicated that there was found significant variation in weed dry weight at harvest among the different treatments during all the three years and in the pooled results.

Significantly the lowest weed dry weight at harvest was recorded in the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) during 2018-19 (17.10 g/m²), 2019-20 (3.85 g/m²) and 2020-21 (16.10 g/m²) and in pooled results (12.35 g/m²) and followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS) during all the three years and in pooled results.

Whereas, significantly the highest weed dry weight at harvest was observed in the control treatment(T₁) during 2018-19 (57.70 g/m²), 2019-20 (35.73 g/m²) and 2020-21 (86.80 g/m²) and in pooled results (60.08 g/m²). Husain et al. (2015) [5] also observed lower dry weight of weed in hand weeding twice treatment compared to chemical weed control and weedy check in linseed.

Weed control efficiency and weed index

The highest weed control efficiency (70.36 %) was recorded with the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS) i.e. 61.53 % in pooled results. The lowest weed index was recorded with T₂ (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS) in pooled results. This might be due to effective weed control achieved under these weed management treatments in terms of reduced biomass of weeds and higher weed control efficiency.

Effect on growth characters

The pooled results pertaining to the growth parameters like plant height, number of branches per plant and stover weight per plant are presented in Table 2. The result revealed that among the different treatments, T₂ treatment (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) recorded significantly higher plant height (61.38 cm), but it remained at par with the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS). In case of number of branches per plant and stover weight per plant, significantly the highest branches (5.56) and stover weight (3.02 g/plant) were recorded under the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) and followed by the treatment T₉

(Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS). Whereas, significantly the lowest plant height (40.62 cm), number of branches per plant (2.43) and stover weight per plant (1.53 g) were recorded with the treatment T₁ (Unweeded -control). All these growth parameters performing best in Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS might be due to initial vigorous crop growth restricted the growth of weeds that has indirectly boosted the plants to record higher growth parameters and also characteristics of better utilization of solar energy and nutrients during plant growth which has contributed for an increased growth of crop and also weed control by different treatments which resulted into less or nearly no crop weed competition for nutrients, light, moisture and space which leads to higher accumulation of photosynthesis. Thus, it clearly indicates that increased weed population adversely affect the yield parameters in linseed.

Effect on yield attributes

Yield attributing characters, that determine the yield, is the resultant of the vegetative development of the plant. Analysis of pooled data showed that all yield attributing characters viz., no. of capsule per plant, no. of seeds per capsule and thousand seed weight were significantly influenced by weed management practices are presented in Table 2.

The results revealed that different treatments had significant effect on all the yield attributes. The treatment T₂ (Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) recorded significantly higher values of number of capsules per plant(27.92), number of seeds per capsule(7.81), test weight(6.27 g) and seed weight per plant(1.23 g/plant) and followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS) in case of capsules per plant and seeds per capsule, while test weight and seed weight per plant, remained at par with the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS).Whereas, significantly the lowest values of all attributes were observed under the control treatment (T₁). Higher growth and yield attributes of linseed in Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS treatment may be due to lowest weed density and weed dry weight observed with this treatment.

Effect on seed and stover yields

The results of the experiment (Table 3) indicated that the different treatments had significant effect on seed and stover yields of linseed during all the years as well as in pooled data. Significantly higher seed yield and stover yield were recorded in the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing), but which was at par with the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS). The higher seed yield of 787, 1083, 870 and 913 kg/ha and higher stover yield of 2191, 2309, 2312 and 2271 kg/ha were recorded with the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) during the year 2018-19, 2019-20, 2020-21 and in pooled results, respectively. While, significantly the lowest seed yield and stover yields were observed in the unweeded -control treatment (T₁) during all the years as well as in pooled results. The results were in line with the findings of Sharma et al. (1997) who reported that hand weeding twice reduced the total weed intensity as compared weedy check in linseed. This may be due to lower weed density and weed biomass registered with this treatments as well as higher growth and yield attributes of linseed. The minimum seed yield (445 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded under weedy check (T₁) treatment due to unhindered growth of weeds. Jain and Agarwal (1998) and Mishra et al. (2003) noticed that the presence of weed throughout the cropping season caused 45.5 per cent reduction in seed yield compared to one hand weeding. Significant yield reduction by weeds (37.9 %) in linseed crop was also observed by Tomar et al. (1990).

Effect on quality parameter

The results pertaining to protein and oil content in seed of linseed are presented in Table 5. The results revealed that different treatments had no any significant variation in protein and oil content in linseed.

Economics

The data pertaining to economics are presented in Table 4. An appraisal of data indicated that the maximum net returns of Rs. 33088/ha was recorded with the treatment T₂ (Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing) followed by the treatment T₉ (Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS).

Conclusion

Based on the results of three years field experiment, it seems quite logical to conclude that for effective management of weeds in linseed, Inter culturing *fb* hand weeding at 20 & 40 days after sowing was effective for producing higher seed yield along with more net monetary returns followed by Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS

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Table: 1 Effect of weed management treatments on total weeds, weed dry weight (gm²), Weed index (%) and weed control efficiency(%)

Treatment		Weed density (No./m ²)	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)	Weed index (%)	Weed control efficiency (%)
T ₁	Unweeded (control)	11.05 (122.56)	-	-	0.00
T ₂	Inter culturing <i>fb</i> hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS	4.73 (23.33)	3.44 (12.35)	0.00	70.36
T ₃	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence	7.36 (54.78)	4.98 (25.92)	18.82	35.01
T ₄	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence	8.49 (72.11)	6.01 (37.02)	25.88	24.26
T ₅	Pendimethalin + Imazethapyr @ 800g/ha as Pre emergence (Ready mix)	8.29 (69.33)	5.85 (35.11)	26.82	20.91
T ₆	Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence	9.50 (90.78)	6.63 (44.74)	40.00	11.44
T ₇	Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	7.48 (55.89)	5.23 (27.99)	14.98	37.61
T ₈	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds(Post emergence)	7.39 (54.89)	5.15 (27.76)	12.94	40.21
T ₉	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	5.41 (29.78)	3.78 (15.12)	4.70	61.53
T ₁₀	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	6.71 (45.56)	4.58 (21.74)	11.76	50.61
	S. Em+	0.11	0.11		
	C.D. at 5 %	0.32	0.32	-	-
	C.V. (%)	4.47	6.25		

* Figures indicating ($\sqrt{X+0.5}$) transformed values, Figures in parenthesis are indicating original values

Table: 2 Growth and yield attributes yield and quality of linseed as influenced by different treatments (Pooled of three years)

Treatment		Plant height (cm)	Number of branches per plant	Number of capsules per plant	Number of seeds per capsule	Test weight (g)	Seed weight per plant (g)
T ₁	Unweeded (control)	40.62	2.43	19.01	5.39	4.48	0.48
T ₂	Inter culturing <i>fb</i> hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS	61.38	5.56	27.92	7.81	6.27	1.23
T ₃	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence	54.02	3.87	24.58	6.67	5.52	0.89
T ₄	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence	49.76	3.52	22.08	6.41	5.33	0.71
T ₅	Pendimethalin + Imazethapyr @ 800g/ha as Pre emergence (Ready mix)	48.91	3.51	22.40	6.40	5.05	0.73
T ₆	Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence	46.10	3.17	20.59	5.90	4.91	0.63
T ₇	Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	52.67	3.86	24.07	6.62	5.48	0.86
T ₈	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds(Post emergence)	53.78	4.07	24.34	6.52	6.05	1.03

T ₉	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	59.27	5.13	26.38	7.28	6.22	1.12
T ₁₀	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	55.93	4.50	25.37	6.82	6.14	0.99
	S. Em ₊	0.91	0.13	0.48	0.16	0.08	0.03
	C.D. at 5 %	2.59	0.36	1.36	0.44	0.22	0.07
	C.V. (%)	5.23	9.68	6.08	7.06	4.22	8.83

Table : 3 Seed, stover yields and relative yield loss of linseed as well as yield loss as influenced by different treatments

Treatment		Seed yield (kg/ha)				Stover yield (kg/ha)				Harvest Index (%)	Relative yield loss (%)
		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Pooled	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Pooled		
T ₁	Unweeded (Control)	378	528	429	445	1496	1324	1389	1403	24.06	51.26
T ₂	Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS	787	1083	870	913	2191	2309	2312	2271	28.56	-
T ₃	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence	639	907	750	765	1713	1923	1762	1799	29.68	16.21
T ₄	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence	583	809	645	679	1646	1790	1694	1710	28.26	25.63
T ₅	Pre mix Pendimethalin +Imazethapyr @ 800g/ha as Pre emergence	576	858	657	697	1556	1716	1602	1625	29.85	23.66
T ₆	Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence	472	753	553	593	1526	1559	1571	1552	27.37	35.05
T ₇	Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	669	867	704	747	1859	1803	1901	1854	28.64	18.18
T ₈	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds(Post emergence)	685	889	735	770	1890	1864	1935	1896	28.82	15.66
T ₉	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	750	1053	846	883	2062	2259	2111	2144	29.03	3.29
T ₁₀	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	695	975	765	812	1938	2065	1975	1993	28.84	11.06
	S.Em ₊	33	40	29	20	81	86	79	48	0.34	-
	C.D. at 5 %	99	118	86	56	242	257	234	134	0.95	
	C.V. (%)	9.28	7.87	7.21	8.13	7.88	8.05	7.48	7.81	3.55	

Table : 4 Cost and return analysis of different weed management treatments

Treatments		Seed yield (kg/ha)	Stover yield (kg/ha)	Total cost of cultivation (Rs./ha)	Gross income (Rs./ha)	Net returns (Rs./ha)	B:C ratio
T ₁	Unweeded (control)	445	1403	28183	35359	7176	1.25
T ₂	Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS	913	2271	37635	70723	33088	1.88
T ₃	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence	765	1799	30224	58947	28723	1.95
T ₄	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence	679	1710	29939	52660	22721	1.76

T ₅	Pre mix Pendimethalin + Imazethapyr @800g/ha as Pre emergence	697	1625	31319	53665	22346	1.71
T ₆	Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence	593	1552	29699	46166	16467	1.55
T ₇	Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	747	1854	30014	57852	27838	1.93
T ₈	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	770	1896	29939	59588	29649	1.99
T ₉	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	883	2144	35784	68242	32458	1.91
T ₁₀	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	812	1993	35499	62819	27320	1.70

Note- Selling price : Seed : Rs.70.00/kg, Stover : Rs. 3.00 Rs./kg

Table : 5 Protein and oil content of linseed as influenced by different treatments (Pooled of three years)

Treatment		Protein content (%)	Oil content (%)
T ₁	Unweeded (control)	18.21	25.32
T ₂	Inter culturing fb hand weeding at 20 & 40 DAS	18.83	26.76
T ₃	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as Pre emergence	18.73	27.58
T ₄	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as Pre emergence	19.09	26.82
T ₅	Pre mix Pendimethalin+Imazethapyr @800g/ha as Pre emergence	18.26	28.43
T ₆	Oxadiargyl @ 75 g/ha as Pre emergence	18.78	28.56
T ₇	Clodinafop @ 60 g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds (Post emergence)	19.35	28.81
T ₈	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha at 2 to 3 leaf stage of weeds(Post emergence)	19.74	28.96
T ₉	Pendimethalin @ 1.0 kg/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	18.75	30.59
T ₁₀	Imazethapyr @ 75g/ha as PE and one hand weeding at 40 DAS	18.96	28.00
	S.Em _±	0.59	1.41
	C.D. at 5 %	NS	NS
	C.V. (%)	5.40	8.75